

ANALYSIS OF BUCKLING CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES OF FG-CNT REINFORCED NANO COMPOSITES

Dr Kulli Dileep Kumar^{1*}

¹Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University College of Engineering Kakinada, Andhra Pradesh

ABSTRACT

In the present study, buckling analysis of FG CNT Reinforced Nano Composite plates will be analyzed. The Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) are well known for its application in the areas of advanced composite materials for their improved elastic properties. This study investigates the buckling loads and buckling pattern of composite plates reinforced with carbon nanotubes with uniform or functionally graded distribution across the plate thickness. For getting elastic and shear modulus we use rule of mixture. The first order Shear Deformation Theory (FSDT) is used to formulate a governing equation to approximate the plate kinematics. The plate is subjected to uniaxial compressive load across the plate thickness. Using the Ritz method the distribution of stress resultants in the plate domain is obtained. Comparison studies are provided to assure the accuracy of the presented formulation for isotropic homogenous and cross-ply laminated plates.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is discovered that the strength and stiffness of Nano composites produced can be considerably enhanced and a significant increase in fracture toughness is also found. They studied the rheological behaviour of compression moulded mixtures of polycarbonate and CNTs using oscillatory rheometry at 260°C. They discovered that 2 wt% nanotubes caused significant improvement in electrical resistivity and complex viscosity. These investigations indicated that the introduction of CNTs into a polymer matrix may remarkably improve mechanical, electrical and thermal properties of the resulting Nano composites.

Carbon nanotubes are of two types

1. Single wall carbon nano tube (SWNT)
2. Multiple wall carbon nano tube (MWNT)

Single wall nanotubes (SWNT) consist of one cylinder. It is made of single graphene sheet rolled up into cylinder closed by two caps (semi fullerenes). The SWNTs have diameter in the range of 0.5 -2.0 nm. The length is in the range of 50-150 μm length. The SWNTs are micro porous and the specific surface area is in the range of 1300 m^2/g (outer surface). SWCNTs are commonly arranged in bundles. SWNTs have less topological defects and have better mechanical and electro physical properties

Multiwall (MWNT) nano tubes consist of many nested concentric SWNTs cylinders with increasing successive radii. The concentric walls are spaced regularly at 0.34 nm similar to inter graphene distance. MWNTs have outer diameter in range of 2 – 100 nm depending on number of coaxial tubes present. An eigenvalue problem is established to obtain the buckling load and buckling shape of the plate. Comparison studies are provided to assure the accuracy of the presented formulation for isotropic homogeneous and cross-ply laminated plates. Afterwards,

parametric studies are performed for composite plates reinforced with carbon nanotubes [1]. The influence of CNT volume fractions, plate length-to thickness ratio, plate aspect ratio, distribution type of CNT and boundary conditions on the buckling responses of the laminated nanocomposite plates are investigated. The effects of number of layers and lamination angle are also examined in detail [2]. To enhance the buckling capacity of the skew plate, CNTs should be dispersed according to the FG-X pattern. In this type of distribution pattern for CNTs, the CNTs are more dispersed near the free surfaces of the plate which results in the enhancement of the flexural rigidities of the plate[3]. The convergence and comparison analysis established the accuracy and reliability of the developed finite element model. Further several numerical examples have been solved by varying the design parameters and following points are concluded from the current finite element analysis [4].

The CF, OP, NOP and PTF functions should be discarded as appropriate for the computation of higher natural frequencies and mode shapes, the SBF functions can be used with some necessary cautions about the numerical stability, while the MCF functions present the better numerical behavior taking into account all the features studied[5]. This paper presents a review of various investigations in the existing literature in terms of static, free vibration, dynamic, buckling and non-linear analyses of FG-CNTRCs[6]. the effects of the volume fractions of CNTs, plate width-to-thickness ratio, plate aspect ratio, distribution type of CNTs and boundary conditions on the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the laminated FG-CNT reinforced composite plates. Besides, the effects of number of layers and lamination angle are also examined[7]. Several examples are given to demonstrate the convergence, accuracy and flexibility of the present method. The effects of the volume fractions of CNTs, distribution type of CNTs, boundary restraint parameters and geometrical parameters on the vibration behavior of the FG-CNTRC truncated conical panels are presented [8]. Vibration responses of the cylindrical shell computed by the FSDT and TSDT are compared to verify the necessity of the high-order shear deformation theory in the vibration analysis for thick CNT reinforced structures [9]. The responses are compared numerically using the direct iteration method in conjunction with the finite element method. The validity and the convergence behavior of the present nonlinear model have been checked and the effects of different design parameters on the nonlinear vibration responses are discussed [10].

Several numerical tests are performed to investigate the influence of the CNTs volume fractions, CNTs distributions, CNTs orientation angles, boundary conditions, length-to-thickness ratios and the number of layers on the frequencies of the laminated FG-CNTRC beams. Moreover, a laminated composite beam combined by various distribution types of CNTs is also studied [11]. The results of this study may serve as a benchmark for future guidelines in designing nanocomposite structures subjected to various moving loads. But our parametric study is only an example, and more studies should be carried out for individual design cases[12]. The nonlinear free vibration of FG-CNTRC beams is studied within the framework of Timoshenko beam theory and von Kármán type displacement–strain relationship. The material properties of FG-CNTRC are assumed to be graded in the thickness and estimated through the rule of mixture [13].the effects of the volume fractions of CNTs, plate width-to-thickness ratio, plate aspect ratio, distribution type of CNTs and boundary conditions on the natural frequencies and mode shapes of the laminated FG-CNT reinforced composite plates. Besides, the effects of number of layers and lamination angle are also examined [14]. Interfacial shear failure, cohesive failure and CNTs pull-out are the dominated failure modes in the SAJs, whereas bearing, shear-out, longitudinal splitting and bolt

fracture are observed for the bolted joints. Considerable attention was given to analyse the scatter in the tensile strength and fatigue life results [15].

There are two major categories leading to the sudden failure of a component: material failure and structural instability, which is often called Buckling. For material failures you need to consider the yield stress for ductile materials and the ultimate stress for brittle materials. When a slender structure is loaded in compression, for small loads it deforms with hardly any noticeable change in geometry and load carrying ability. Design of structures is often based on strength and stiffness considerations. Strength is defined to be the ability of the structure to withstand the applied load, while stiffness *is* the resistance to deformation (i.e., the structure is sufficiently stiff not to deform beyond permissible limits). However, a structure may become unstable (in the sense described above) long before the strength and stiffness criteria are violated. Linear elastic bifurcation buckling of structural members is the most elementary form of buckling, and its study is an essential step towards understanding the buckling behavior of complex structures, including structures incorporating inelastic behavior, initial imperfections, residual stresses, etc.

2. PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE MATERILAS

The moduli and Poisson's ratio of a fibre-reinforced material can be expressed in terms of the moduli, Poisson's ratios, and volume fractions of the constituents. To this end, let

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= E_f v_f + E_m v_m \\ E_2 &= \frac{E_f E_m}{E_f v_m + E_m v_f} \\ \vartheta_{12} &= \vartheta_f v_f + \vartheta_m v_m \\ G_{12} &= \frac{G_f G_m}{G_f v_m + G_m v_f} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where E_1 is the longitudinal modulus, E_2 is transverse modulus, ϑ_{12} is the major Poisson's ratio, and G_{12} is the shear modulus $E_f =$ modulus of the fibre; $E_m =$ modulus of the matrix $\vartheta_f =$ Poisson's ratio of the fibre; $\vartheta_m =$ Poisson's ratio of the matrix $v_f =$ fibre volume fraction; $v_m =$ matrix volume fraction

Generally, the effective mechanical properties of the FG-CNTRC rectangular plate are obtained using the well-known homogenization schemes, such as Mori-Tanaka scheme or the rule of mixtures. For the sake of simplicity, in the present research, the rule of mixtures is used to obtain the properties of the composite plate. However, to account for the scale-dependent properties of nanocomposite media, efficiency parameters are introduced. The refined rule of mixture approach which contains the efficiency parameters has been used extensively in analysis of FG-CNTRC beams, plates, panels, and shells. According to the rule, the effective material properties may be written as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= \eta_1 V_{CN} E_{11}^{CN} + V_m E^m \\ \frac{\eta_2}{E_{22}} &= \frac{V_{CN}}{E_{22}^{CN}} + \frac{V_m}{E^m} \\ \frac{\eta_3}{G_{12}} &= \frac{V_{CN}}{G_{12}^{CN}} + \frac{V_m}{G^m} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the above equations, η_1 , η_2 , and η_3 are the so-called efficiency parameters which as mentioned earlier are introduced to account for the size-dependent material properties of the plate. These constants are chosen to equal the obtained values of Young's modulus and shear modulus from the present modified rule of mixtures with the results obtained according to the molecular dynamics simulations. Besides E_{11}^{CN} , E_{22}^{CN} and G_{12}^{CN} are the elasticity modulus and shear modulus of SWCNTs, respectively. Furthermore, E^m and G^m indicate the corresponding properties of the isotropic matrix. The volume fraction of CNTs and matrix is denoted by V_{CN} and V_m , respectively, which satisfy the condition

3. BUCKLING OF ORTHOTROPIC PLATES

Composite laminates are formed by stacking layers of different composite material and/or fibre orientation. By construction, composite laminates have their planar dimensions one to two orders of magnitude larger than their thickness. Often laminates are used in applications that require membrane and bending strengths. Therefore, composite laminates are treated as plate elements

3.1 Uniaxial Tension

Consider a rectangular plate simply supported along its four edges, made of an orthotropic laminate. This plate is subjected to a uniform compression on each edge, with respective resultants N_x and N_y . The buckling equation is deduced with $q = 0$ (no transverse load), thus:

Figure 1 Rectangular Plate Subjected to Biaxial Compression

$$D_{11} \frac{\partial^4 w_0}{\partial x^4} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66}) \frac{\partial^4 w_0}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_{22} \frac{\partial^4 w_0}{\partial y^4} = N_x \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} + N_y \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} \quad (3)$$

The boundary conditions are:

- along the edges $x = 0$ and $x = a$:

$$w_0 = 0, M_x = -D_{11} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} - D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

- along the edges $y = 0$ and $y = b$:

$$w_0 = 0, M_y = -D_{12} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial x^2} - D_{22} \frac{\partial^2 w_0}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

These conditions are satisfied with a deflection of the form:

$$w_0(x, y) = A_{mn} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{n\pi y}{b} \tag{4}$$

Substituting this expression into equation we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &\pi^2 A_{mn} [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4] \\ &= -A_{mn}(N_x m^2 + N_y n^2 R^2) a^2 \end{aligned}$$

Where R is the length-to-width ratio.

A nonzero solution of the buckling problem leads to the expression for the resultants

$$N_x m^2 + N_y n^2 R^2 = -\frac{\pi^2}{a^2} [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4]$$

We consider the case of a uniform compression on each edge of the form:

$$N_x = -N_0, \quad N_y = -\alpha N_0$$

Where N_0 is positive. Equation leads to:

$$N_0 = \frac{\pi^2 [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4]}{a^2(m^2 + \alpha n^2 R^2)} \tag{5}$$

The critical buckling load corresponds to the values of m and n leading to the lowest values of N_0 .

We study various types of loadings.

3.2 Uniaxial Compression

In the case of uniaxial compression in the x-direction we have $a = 0$, and equation becomes

$$N_0 = \frac{\pi^2}{m^2 a^2} [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2R^2 + D_{22}n^4R^4] \tag{6}$$

For a given m , the smallest value of N_0 is obtained for $n = 1$, that is:

$$N_0 = \frac{\pi^2}{m^2 a^2} [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2R^2 + D_{22}R^4]$$

The buckling load depends upon the length-to-width ratio of the plate. In fact, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta N_0 &= N_0(m + 1) - N_0(m) \\ &= \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} D_{22} \frac{2m+1}{m^2(m+1)^2} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} m^2(m + 1)^2 - R^4 \right] \end{aligned}$$

The value of ΔN_0 changes sign for:

$$R = R_m = [m(m + 1)]^{1/2} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \right)^{1/4}$$

From this it results that:

- If $R \leq R_m$: $N_{cr} = N_0(m)$,
- If $R \geq R_m$: $N_{cr} = N_0(m + 1)$,

For the first values of m this leads to:

- for $R \leq \sqrt{2} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \right)^{1/4}$:

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} [D_{11} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})R^2 + D_{22}R^4]$$

- for $\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \right)^{1/4} \leq R \leq \sqrt{6} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \right)^{1/4}$:

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{4a^2} [16D_{11} + 8(D_{12} + 2D_{66})R^2 + D_{22}R^4]$$

- for $\sqrt{6} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}\right)^{1/4} \leq R \leq \sqrt{12} \left(\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}}\right)^{1/4}$:

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2}{9a^2} [81D_{11} + 18(D_{12} + 2D_{66})R^2 + D_{22}R^4]$$

The variation of the critical buckling load as a function of the length-to-width ratio of the plate for

$$D_{11} = D_{22}, \quad D_{12} + 2D_{66} = 0.7D_{22}$$

For the values of the length-to-width ratio, two buckled mode shapes leading to the same value of the critical load are possible:

$$w_0 = A_{m1} \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b}$$

and

$$w_0 = A_{m+1,1} \sin \frac{(m+1)\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b}$$

3.3 Square Plate under Biaxial Compression

In the case of a square plate subjected to biaxial compression of the same value on both edges, we have $a = 1$ and $R = 1$. Equation may be written:

$$N_0 = \frac{\pi^2 [D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})m^2n^2 + D_{22}n^4]}{a^2(m^2 + n^2)} \quad (7)$$

This expression shows that for $D_{11} \geq D_{22}$ the smallest value of N_0 is obtained for $m = 1$, that is:

$$N_0 = \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} D_{22} \frac{1}{1 + n^2} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} + 2 \frac{(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{D_{22}} n^2 + n^4 \right] \quad (8)$$

For $n = 1$:

$$N_0 = N_0(1) = \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} D_{22} \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} + 2 \frac{(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{D_{22}} + 1 \right] \quad (9)$$

And for $n = 2$:

$$N_0 = N_0(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{a^2} D_{22} \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} + 8 \frac{(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{D_{22}} + 16 \right] \quad (10)$$

Comparison of equations and shows that in the case where:

$$\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \leq 2 \frac{(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{D_{22}} + 9 \quad (11)$$

The buckling load corresponds to $n = 1$, that is:

$$N_{cr} = N_0(1)$$

And the buckling mode is:

$$w_0 = A_{11} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{\pi y}{b} \quad (12)$$

In the case where:

$$\frac{D_{11}}{D_{22}} \geq 2 \frac{(D_{12} + 2D_{66})}{D_{22}} + 9$$

The critical buckling load corresponds to $n = 2$, that is:

$$N_{cr} = N_0(2)$$

And the buckling mode is:

$$w_0 = A_{12} \sin \frac{\pi x}{a} \sin \frac{2\pi y}{b}$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The aim beyond the present study and the developed procedure in the previous steps is to study the buckling characteristics of carbon nanotube-reinforced composite plates subjected to non-uniform compression at the boundaries. In a CSCF plate, the first letter is associated with $x = -0.5a$, the second letter is the boundary condition at $y = -0.5b$, the third letter denotes the boundary conditions at $x = +0.5a$, and finally the last letter is associated with the boundary at $y = +0.5b$

Table 1 Critical buckling load parameter, λ_{cr} for FG-CNTRC plates with $b/h = 50$ and $V_{CN}^* = 0.17$

B.Cs.	Pattern	a/b							
		0.4	0.5	0.6	0.8	1	1.5	2	3
CCCC	FG-X	741.9354	615.1135	510.3886	359.5975	264.7015	151.9828	115.2727	97.9234
	UD	619.8654	493.2214	396.3208	267.5472	192.5509	110.1589	86.6188	72.3625
	FG-O	429.1789	319.2788	244.7754	156.6488	110.7794	66.6287	58.1058	46.9493
CCCF	FG-X	741.9548	615.1019	510.3278	359.2183	263.4763	145.7887	98.6666	56.3504
	UD	619.876	493.2057	396.255	267.1413	191.285	104.032	70.35	39.59
	FG-O	429.178	319.2504	244.6712	156.0677	109.1598	59.4595	40.1736	22.3404
CCFF	FG-X	117.1918	80.6285	59.8639	38.7409	28.4249	16.5968	12.3487	10.7451
	UD	82.1086	56.3175	41.9304	27.3578	20.1206	11.9494	9.2753	8.4813
	FG-O	44.935	31.045	23.4075	15.5325	11.5154	7.3203	6.2787	6.032
CFFF	FG-X	116.8346	79.6928	58.1866	35.5386	24.1831	11.5853	6.6811	3.0154
	UD	81.7245	55.3839	40.3372	24.5427	16.5956	7.8515	4.5064	2.0273
	FG-O	44.4249	29.9926	21.8045	13.1404	8.7645	4.062	2.3145	1.0357

Table 1 presents the critical buckling load parameter of FG-CNTRC plates for three different distribution patterns, eight aspect ratios, and eight different sets of boundary conditions. The side-to-thickness ratio is set equal to $b/h = 30$ and the volume fraction of CNT is chosen as $V_{CN}^* = 0.17$. Results of this Table indicate that buckling loads of FG-X plates are higher than, in order, UD and FG-O plates. As expected, plates with all edges clamped have the highest buckling loads.

Figure 2 Buckling load parameter as a function of aspect ratio for UD CNTRC plates with $a/h = 30$, at CCCC boundary condition, and different volume fractions of CNTs

Figure 3 Buckling load parameter as a function of aspect ratio for UD CNTRC plates with $a/h = 30$, at CCCF boundary condition, and different volume fractions of CNTs

Figure 4 Buckling load parameter as a function of aspect ratio for UD CNTRC plates with $a/h = 30$, at CCFF boundary condition, and different volume fractions of CNTs

Figure 5 Buckling load parameter as a function of aspect ratio for UD CNTRC plates with $a/h = 30$, at CFFF boundary condition, and different volume fractions of CNTs

Figure 6 Fundamental buckling mode shape of $w_0(x, y)$ in FG-CNTRC plates with FG-X pattern, at $V^*_{CN} = 0.17$, $a/b = 1$, $b/h = 50$, CCCC boundary condition.

Figure 7 Fundamental buckling mode shape of $w_0(x, y)$ in FG-CNTRC plates with FG-X pattern, at $V^*_{CN} = 0.17$, $a/b = 1$, $b/h = 50$, CFFF boundary condition.

Figures 2 to 3 Fundamental buckling mode shape of $w_0(x, y)$ in FG-CNTRC plates with FG-X pattern, at $V_{CN}^* = 0.17$, $a/b = 1$, $b/h = 50$,

Figures 4 to 5 provides the critical buckling load parameter of FG-X and UD plates, respectively. In each Figure, six types of boundary conditions and three different volume fractions of CNTs are considered. It is verified that the buckling loads of the plate enhance as the volume fraction of CNTs increases. This effect is due to the higher elasticity modulus of CNTs in comparison with the elasticity modulus of the polymeric matrix. Comparison of the results for Figures verifies that the critical buckling load of an FG-X plate is higher than of a plate with UD pattern.

Figures 6 to 7 Buckling mode shapes for some selected geometrical characteristics and CNT properties are provided in Figs. The presentations of these Figures are associated with the results of Table 2 with FG-X pattern. As seen from the fundamental buckling mode shape, the essential boundary conditions are satisfied at the supports. Furthermore, a comparison between the results of Figs accepts that the buckled shape of the plate is highly sensitive to the aspect ratio of the plate

5. CONCLUSIONS

Most of the available works on the subject of linear stability examination of FG-CNTRC plates are based on uniform edge compression. In this research, buckling loads and mode shapes of rectangular FG-CNTRC plates subjected to parabolic edge compression are obtained using a Ritz formulation.

- At first, the distribution of in-plane loads within the plate domain is obtained by means of a two-dimensional formulation.
- Afterwards, an eigenvalue problem is formulated using the Chebyshev–Ritz method.
- Accuracy and correctness of the presented formulation are demonstrated by comparison with the available data for isotropic homogeneous and cross-ply laminated composite plates.
- Afterwards, numerical results are given for a stability analysis of FG-CNTRC plates subjected to parabolic loading.

As shown, the distribution of in-plane loads within the plate is different from the applied parabolic loads at the boundary

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